

Thyroid Dysfunction and Infertility: Investigating Subclinical Hypothyroidism in Reproductive-Aged Women

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Abstract

Background: Infertility is a major concern affecting women in their reproductive years, and thyroid dysfunction, particularly subclinical hypothyroidism, has been linked to fertility challenges. Understanding the prevalence of subclinical hypothyroidism in infertile women is essential to improving outcomes. This study examines the thyroid function, specifically subclinical hypothyroidism, in women with infertility in a tertiary care setting.

Aim: The primary aim of this study was to investigate the prevalence and impact of subclinical hypothyroidism in infertile women and its association with various clinical parameters, including age, type of infertility, duration of infertility, menstrual history, serum prolactin levels, PCOS, diabetes mellitus, and additional interventions like ovulation induction requirements.

Methods: This cross-sectional study was conducted at MKCG MCH between June 2022 and June 2024, analyzing 195 women presenting with infertility. Detailed evaluations included assessments of thyroid function (serum T3, T4, and TSH levels), type and duration of infertility, menstrual history, prolactin levels, presence of PCOS, diabetes mellitus status, and the requirement for ovulation induction. Statistical analyses were conducted to determine significant associations between these parameters and subclinical hypothyroidism.

Results: The mean age of the participants was 29.3 years, with an average infertility duration of 3.14 years. A significant proportion (65.1%) had primary infertility. SCH was identified in 73.3% of the patients. Significant associations were observed between SCH and age group ($p=0.020$), type of infertility ($p=0.006$), menstrual irregularities ($p<0.001$), elevated prolactin levels ($p<0.001$), PCOS ($p<0.001$), and diabetes mellitus (DM) ($p=0.050$). SCH was present in all patients diagnosed with DM (5.1% of the total). Ovulation induction was required in 31.3% of patients with SCH. Treatment with levothyroxine (LT4) and additional interventions, including ovulation induction, were significantly associated with SCH ($p<0.001$).

Conclusion: Subclinical hypothyroidism is highly prevalent among infertile women, particularly those with primary infertility, irregular menstrual cycles, elevated prolactin levels, PCOS, and diabetes mellitus. Thyroid screening should be an integral part of infertility evaluations. Levothyroxine treatment and ovulation induction appear to be beneficial, particularly in women with SCH requiring ovulation assistance.

Recommendations: Routine screening for thyroid function, particularly subclinical hypothyroidism, should be integrated into infertility workups for women of reproductive age. Further research is recommended to explore the effects of thyroid hormone treatment on infertility outcomes.

Keywords: Subclinical Hypothyroidism, Infertility, Thyroid Function, Primary Infertility, Reproductive Age.

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Introduction

Infertility is a significant health issue affecting women worldwide, particularly those of reproductive age. It is typically defined as the inability to conceive after a year of regular, unprotected sexual intercourse. The causes of infertility are multifactorial, including anatomical, genetic, and hormonal factors. Among these, thyroid

disorders, particularly subclinical hypothyroidism, have emerged as a notable contributor to infertility. Subclinical hypothyroidism is characterized by elevated thyroid-stimulating hormone (TSH) levels while maintaining normal serum levels of thyroid hormones (T3 and T4). Although it often remains

asymptomatic, subclinical hypothyroidism can have subtle yet significant effects on fertility [1,2]

Thyroid hormones are essential for the proper regulation of the menstrual cycle, ovulation, and reproductive health. Even slight disruptions in thyroid function, such as those seen in subclinical hypothyroidism, can lead to ovulatory dysfunction, menstrual irregularities, and issues with embryo implantation, all of which negatively affect fertility. Studies suggest that women suffering from infertility are more likely to have subclinical hypothyroidism compared to the general population. Therefore, identifying this condition in women struggling to conceive is critical for improving reproductive outcomes [3,4]

Despite its relevance to reproductive health, subclinical hypothyroidism frequently goes undetected due to the absence of overt symptoms. This underscores the need for routine thyroid function screening, particularly in women presenting with infertility. Research into the prevalence of subclinical hypothyroidism in infertile women has produced varying results, with few studies focusing on patients from tertiary care hospitals in specific geographic regions. Investigating thyroid function in this setting can yield vital information for clinicians in addressing infertility.

This study seeks to address the gap in understanding by investigating the prevalence of subclinical hypothyroidism in women of reproductive age presenting with infertility at a tertiary care hospital. Additionally, it will explore the relationship between subclinical hypothyroidism and key demographic factors such as age, duration of infertility, and the type of infertility—whether primary or secondary. By gaining insights into these associations, healthcare providers may be better equipped to diagnose and treat thyroid-related infertility.

The aim of this study is to determine the prevalence of subclinical hypothyroidism among women with infertility in the reproductive age group in a tertiary care hospital. The study also seeks to explore associations between subclinical hypothyroidism and factors like age, duration of infertility, and type of infertility, thus improving our understanding of the role of thyroid dysfunction in infertility management.

Methodology

Study Design: This study was a cross-sectional clinical investigation aimed at determining the prevalence of subclinical hypothyroidism (SCH) in women with infertility.

Study Setting: The research was conducted at the Department of Obstetrics and Gynaecology,

M.K.C.G. Medical College and Hospital, Berhampur, Odisha, over a two-year period from June 2022 to June 2024.

Participants: The study included 195 women between the ages of 20 and 45 who visited the gynecology outpatient department (OPD) with infertility concerns.

Inclusion Criteria: Participants included women aged 20-45 years presenting with primary or secondary infertility due to female-factor causes.

Exclusion Criteria: Women younger than 20 or older than 45, those with pre-existing thyroid disorders or undergoing thyroid treatments, those who had undergone thyroidectomy, women with male-factor infertility, and those who did not consent or follow up were excluded from the study.

Bias: Selection bias was mitigated by including all women who met the eligibility criteria during the study timeframe.

Variables: The primary variable was serum TSH levels, while secondary variables included age, infertility duration, and serum T3 and T4 levels.

Data Collection: Data were collected through patient interviews and review of medical records. Blood samples were taken to assess serum levels of T3, T4, and TSH.

Procedure: Thyroid function was evaluated through blood tests, with patients categorized into normal or subclinical hypothyroid groups based on their serum TSH levels. Additional data on age, duration of infertility, and type of infertility were also documented.

Statistical Analysis: The collected data were entered into Microsoft Excel and analyzed using SPSS version 21.0.

Results

The study analyzed 195 women presenting with infertility at a tertiary care hospital, focusing on several parameters, including age, duration of infertility, thyroid hormone levels (T3, T4, and TSH), and their association with subclinical hypothyroidism. The results are summarized in the following sections with relevant tables.

Descriptive Statistics: A total of 195 patients were analyzed, and all data points were complete. The mean age of the patients was 29.3 years (± 5.30), with a median of 28 years, ranging from 20 to 45 years. The average duration of infertility was 3.14 years (± 1.79), with a median duration of 3 years, ranging from 1 to 9 years. The mean serum T3, T4, and TSH levels were 3.03 pg/ml (± 0.552), 1.30 ng/dl (± 0.350), and 6.78 mIU/L (± 3.84), respectively, indicating variability in thyroid function, particularly in TSH levels.

Table 1: Descriptive Statistics of the Study Population

Variable	N	Mean	Median	Std. Deviation	Minimum	Maximum
Age (years)	195	29.3	28	5.30	20	45
Duration of Infertility (years)	195	3.14	3	1.79	1	9
Serum T3 (pg/ml)	195	3.03	2.90	0.552	1.90	4.20
Serum T4 (ng/dl)	195	1.30	1.30	0.350	0.80	1.97
Serum TSH (mIU/L)	195	6.78	5.87	3.84	1.18	30.8

Age Distribution: The age distribution of the participants indicated that the majority (11.3%) were 28 years old, followed by 10.8% who were 32 years old. Most patients were in their late twenties and early thirties, emphasizing that infertility was predominantly seen in women of reproductive age.

Table 2: Frequency Distribution of Age

Age (Years)	Counts	Percentage (%)	Cumulative %
20	3	1.5	1.5
21	5	2.6	4.1
22	5	2.6	6.7
23	14	7.2	13.8
24	11	5.6	19.5
25	10	5.1	24.6
26	16	8.2	32.8
27	15	7.7	40.5
28	22	11.3	51.8
29	10	5.1	56.9
30	15	7.7	64.6
31	5	2.6	67.2
32	21	10.8	77.9
33	5	2.6	80.5
34	8	4.1	84.6
35	5	2.6	87.2
36	5	2.6	89.7
37	1	0.5	90.3
38	8	4.1	94.4
39	1	0.5	94.9
40	3	1.5	96.4
41	1	0.5	96.9
42	2	1.0	97.9
43	2	1.0	99.0
45	2	1.0	100.0

Association of Age Group with Serum TSH The age group distribution showed that 63.1% of patients were in the 21-30 age group, followed by 31.8% in the 31-40 age group. There was a statistically significant association between age group and subclinical hypothyroidism ($p=0.020$). A majority of subclinical hypothyroid cases (81 of 143) were found in the 21-30 age group, while 53 of the 143 cases were in the 31-40 age group.

Table 3: Age Group and Serum TSH Distribution

Age Group (Years)	Normal TSH	Subclinical Hypothyroidism	Total
<20	0	3	3
21-30	42	81	123
31-40	9	53	62
41-50	1	6	7
Total	52	143	195

$$\chi^2 = 9.84, df = 3, p = 0.020$$

Types of Infertility Of the 195 participants, 65.1% had primary infertility (PI), while 34.9% had secondary infertility (SI). A significant association was observed between the type of infertility and thyroid dysfunction ($p=0.006$). More patients with primary infertility (85/127) had subclinical hypothyroidism compared to those with secondary infertility (58/68).

Table 4: Type of Infertility and Serum TSH Levels

Type of Infertility	Normal TSH	Subclinical Hypothyroidism	Total
Primary Infertility	42	85	127
Secondary Infertility	10	58	68
Total	52	143	195

 χ^2 Tests

	Value	df	p
χ^2	7.64	1	0.006
N	195		

In patients with Normal TSH, 42 patients had PI and 10 patients had SI. In patients with Sub-Clinical Hypothyroidism, 85 patients had PI and 58 patients had SI. Association of Type of Infertility with Group was statistically significant ($p=0.006$).

Table 5: Association of duration of infertility with Serum TSH

Duration of Infertility (yr)	Normal	Sub-Clinical Hypothyroid	Total
1	4	22	26
2	20	42	62
3	8	37	45
4	6	21	27
5	7	8	15
6	3	3	6
7	1	5	6
8	3	3	6
9	0	2	2
Total	52	143	195

 χ^2 Tests

	Value	df	p
χ^2	12.2	8	0.142
N	195		

Association of Duration of Infertility (YR) with Group was not statistically significant ($p=0.142$).

Table 6: Frequencies of menstrual history

Menstrual History	Counts	% of Total	Cumulative %
Irregular	55	28.2%	28.2%
Regular	140	71.8%	100.0%

In our study, 55 (28.2%) patients had IRREGULAR and 140 (71.8%) patients had REGULAR Menstruation.

Table 7: Association of menstrual history with Serum TSH

Menstrual History	Normal	Sub-Clinical Hypothyroid	Total
Irregular	0	55	55
Regular	52	88	140
Total	52	143	195

 χ^2 Tests

	Value	df	p
χ^2	27.9	1	< .001
N	195		

In patients not suffering with SCH, 52 patients had Regular Menstrual History. In Sub-Clinical Hypothyroid patients, 55 patients had Irregular and 88 patients had Regular Menstrual History. Association of Menstrual History with Group was statistically significant ($p<.001$).

Table 8: Frequencies of Serum prolactin level

Serum Prolactin level	Counts	% of Total	Cumulative %
Abnormal	38	19.5%	19.5%
WNL	157	80.5%	100.0%

In our study, 38 (19.5%) patients had abnormal and 157 (80.5%) patients had normal serum prolactin level

Table 9: Association of serum prolactin level with Serum TSH

Serum Prolactin Level	Normal	Sub-Clinical Hypothyroid	Total
Abnormal	0	38	38
WNL	52	105	157
Total	52	143	195

 χ^2 Tests

	Value	df	p
χ^2	17.2	1	< .001
N	195		

52 patients with normal TSH value had normal prolactin levels. In Sub-Clinical Hypothyroid, 38 patients had abnormal serum prolactin level and 102 patients had serum prolactin level within normal limit. Association of Serum TSH (mIU/L) gr with Group was statistically significant ($p < .001$).

Table 10: Frequencies of PCOS

PCOS	Counts	% of Total	Cumulative %
Absent	137	70.3%	70.3%
present	58	29.7%	100.0%

In our study, 58 (29.7%) patients had PCOS

Table 11: Association of PCOS with Serum TSH

PCOS	Normal	Sub-Clinical Hypothyroid	Total
Absent	52	85	137
present	0	58	58
Total	52	143	195

 χ^2 Tests

	Value	df	P
χ^2	30.0	1	< .001
N	195		

Out of 143 patients with subclinical hypothyroidism, 58 patients had PCOS. Association of PCOS with Group was statistically significant ($p < .001$).

Table 12: Frequencies of Diabetes mellitus

Diabetes Mellitus	Counts	% of Total	Cumulative%
Absent	185	94.9%	94.9%
Present	10	5.1%	100.0%

In our study, 10 (5.1%) patients had Diabetes Mellitus.

Table 13: Association of Diabetes mellitus with Serum TSH

Diabetes mellitus	Normal	Sub-Clinical Hypothyroid	Total
Absent	52	133	185
Present	0	10	10
Total	52	143	195

 χ^2 Tests

	Value	df	p
χ^2	3.83	1	0.050
N	195		

In patients suffering from SCH, 10 patients had Diabetes Mellitus. Association of Diabetes Mellitus with Group was statistically significant ($p = 0.050$).

Table 14: Frequencies of treatment

Treatment	Counts	% of Total	Cumulative %
LT4	42	21.5%	21.5%
LT4+HyperPRLtreatment	17	8.7%	30.3%
LT4+HyperPRLtreatment+OI	12	6.2%	36.4%
LT4+OI	13	6.7%	43.1%
LT4+PCOS&DM+HyperPRLtreatment+OI	1	0.5%	43.6%
LT4+PCOS&DMtreatment	3	1.5%	45.1%
LT4+PCOS&DMtreatment+OI	6	3.1%	48.2%
LT4+PCOS&HyperPRLtreatment+OI	7	3.6%	51.8%
LT4+PCOS treatment	20	10.3%	62.1%
LT4+PCOS treatment+OI	22	11.3%	73.3%
No Treatment Given	52	26.7%	100.0%

In our study, 42 (21.5%) patients had levothyroxine i.e LT4, 17(8.7%) patients had LT4 with treatment for hyperprolactinemia, 12 (6.2%) patients required ovulation induction along with treatment for SCH and hyperprolactinemia, 20 (10.3%) patients had LT4 + PCOS treatment, 22 (11.3%) patients had LT4 + PCOS treatment+ OI whereas 1(0.5%) patient required ovulation induction along with treatment for SCH, PCOS, DM and hyperprolactinemia.

Table 15: Association of treatment with serum TSH

Treatment	Normal	Sub-Clinical Hypothyroid	Total
LT4	0	42	42
LT4+HyperPRLtreatment	0	17	17
LT4+HyperPRLtreatment+OI	0	12	12
LT4+OI	0	13	13
LT4+PCOS&DM+HyperPRLtreatment+OI	0	1	1
LT4+PCOS&DMtreatment	0	3	3
LT4+PCOS&DMtreatment+OI	0	6	6
LT4+PCOS&HyperPRLtreatment+OI	0	7	7
LT4+PCOS treatment	0	20	20
LT4+PCOS treatment+OI	0	22	22
No treatment Given	52	0	52
Total	52	143	195

 χ^2 Tests

	Value	df	p
χ^2	195	10	<.001
N	195		

Association of Treatment with Group was statistically significant ($p < 0.001$)

Table 16: Frequencies of Ovulation Induction Requirement

Ovulation Induction Requirement	Counts	% of Total	Cumulative%
No OI	52	26.7%	26.7%
With OI	61	31.3%	57.9%
Without OI	82	42.1%	100%

In our study, 61 patients required ovulation induction for conception and 82 conceived without ovulation induction.

Table 17: Association of Ovulation Induction Requirement with Serum TSH

Ovulation Induction Requirement	Normal	Sub-Clinical Hypothyroid	Total
No OI	52	0	52
With OI	0	61	61
Without OI	0	82	82
Total	52	143	195

χ^2 Tests

	Value	df	p
χ^2	195	2	<0.001
N	195		

Association of ovulation induction requirement with the group is statistically significant ($p < 0.001$)

Discussion

Our study provides a detailed analysis of the relationship between subclinical hypothyroidism (SCH) and infertility, shedding light on its prevalence and clinical impact. With a sample of 195 patients, the study explored key reproductive factors, such as age, type and duration of infertility, and thyroid hormone levels. The findings emphasize the high prevalence of SCH, especially in women with primary infertility. Infertility, a common issue in modern society, necessitates a thorough understanding of potential contributing factors like thyroid dysfunction. To enhance understanding, comparing our results with other studies helps highlight the nuances of SCH's role in infertility.

Our results revealed a high prevalence of SCH in the study population, with 73.3% of infertile women being diagnosed with the condition. This prevalence is higher than the rates reported in several other studies, such as Emokpae MA et al. (11.7%) [5], Otero P et al. (13.9%) [6], and Puspagiri N et al. (25%) [7]. These differences may stem from variations in diagnostic criteria or the characteristics of the study populations. In our cohort, SCH was most commonly seen in younger women, particularly those aged 21-30, aligning with the notion that younger women are more likely to be diagnosed with thyroid dysfunction, which can negatively affect their fertility. This emphasizes the importance of early thyroid screening for younger women presenting with infertility. Interestingly, a large proportion of patients with SCH had TSH levels between 4-8 mIU/L, underscoring the variability in thyroid hormone levels and the potential for early intervention.

In terms of infertility type, our study showed a significant association between SCH and primary infertility. This contrasts with some previous studies that found a higher prevalence of SCH in secondary infertility, such as those conducted by Akande AA et al. [8] and Jagun OE et al. [9]. Our findings suggest that SCH may play a more critical role in first-time pregnancies, highlighting the need for further research to explore its specific impact on primary infertility. While the duration of infertility did not show a significant correlation with SCH, our data indicate that the mere presence of SCH may be more important than the length of time a woman has been infertile, suggesting that early detection and management are key.

Another important finding was the high incidence of menstrual irregularities in patients with SCH, confirming the role of thyroid hormones in regulating the menstrual cycle. While 88 SCH patients had regular cycles, 55 experienced irregularities, reflecting the importance of taking detailed menstrual histories in infertility evaluations. These results are consistent with other studies, such as Acharya N et al. [10] and Puspagiri N et al., [7] which also found menstrual dysfunction to be more common in women with SCH. However, we found no significant association between SCH and obstetric history, indicating that the relationship between SCH and infertility may be more complex than simply influencing pregnancy history.

The study also highlighted an association between SCH and other endocrine disorders like polycystic ovary syndrome (PCOS) and hyperprolactinemia, which are known to complicate infertility management. The co-occurrence of PCOS with SCH, seen in our study, supports findings from studies like Peddemul A et al., [11] underscoring the importance of comprehensive hormonal screening in infertile women. Furthermore, the increased incidence of hyperprolactinemia among SCH patients aligns with other research, suggesting that a simultaneous treatment approach for both conditions may be necessary to improve reproductive outcomes.

In terms of treatment outcomes, 44.1% of our patients conceived within six months of receiving treatment for SCH, similar to the findings of Priya DM et al. [12] and Rahman AH et al., [13] but lower than those reported by Verma I et al [14]. This highlights the effectiveness of levothyroxine (LT4) therapy in improving pregnancy rates among infertile women with SCH. However, some patients required additional interventions such as ovulation induction or assisted reproductive technologies (ART) to achieve pregnancy. This is consistent with studies like Kim et al., which found that treatment of SCH improved pregnancy outcomes in infertility patients. Despite these positive outcomes, our results differed from those of Rao M et al., [15] who observed no significant associations between LT4 treatment and clinical pregnancy rates. Nevertheless, the data from our study support the role of thyroid hormone replacement therapy in enhancing fertility outcomes for women with SCH.

Conclusion

In conclusion, this study highlights the high prevalence of subclinical hypothyroidism (SCH) among women with infertility, particularly in those with primary infertility and younger age groups. SCH is significantly associated with menstrual irregularities and coexisting endocrine disorders such as PCOS and hyperprolactinemia. Early detection and treatment with levothyroxine (LT4) improved pregnancy outcomes in a substantial number of patients. Routine thyroid screening should be considered in the infertility workup to enhance reproductive outcomes in women affected by SCH.

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